

The Rustamid Woman and Her Influence on Ibadi Islamic Heritage The Sister of Aflah and the Sister of Amrūs as Models

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Abstract

Women in medieval Maghreb occupied a high position in Rustumid society, as sources mention a number of them who were not only wives of imams and jurists, but they had a deep jurisprudential, intellectual and historical imprint, which they drew with their prominent works and which continued to be passed on by tongues in gatherings and transmitted by pens in the pages of books.

The Rustumid state (160-296 AH) was known for its capital, Tahert, nicknamed the Iraq of the Maghreb, and for its rich, infallible library, which sources mention was burned by the soldiers of Abu Abdullah al-Shi'i in the year 296 AH. There is no doubt that it contained thousands of volumes in all kinds of sciences and arts, some of which were written locally and some of which were brought from other regions. The Rustumid Ibadi women had a significant share of those volumes, and we are about to mention examples of those women who left a legacy of jurisprudence, history, doctrine, and various fields. Perhaps the oral heritage passed down through generations, which was mentioned by Ibadi sources in general and books of biography in particular, This is the best evidence of the ability of Ibadi women in the Rustumid era to compete with men in gatherings for remembrance, knowledge, preaching and fatwas, and their femininity did not prevent them from excelling and holding or participating in debate sessions.

Therefore, we pose a question about the biographies of both the sister of Imam Aflah al-Rustumi and the sister of Amrus ibn Fath al-Masakani, and the extent of their contributions to the Ibadi and Islamic intellectual heritage in general, as examples of learned Ibadi Rustumid women. Using a historical and descriptive approach, we can examine the most important milestones in the lives of each of them.

This is the sister of Imam al-Rustumi, Aflah ibn Abd al-Wahhab al-Tiharti (3rd century AH), who was well versed in astronomy and rivaled her brother, the Imam, demonstrating the prevalence of this knowledge among women as well as men. And this is the sister of Amrus ibn Fath al-Masakani al-Nafusi (250-300 AH), who attained a high degree of proficiency in various scientific fields. She and her brother are credited with copying the jurisprudential collection entitled "The Ibadi Jurisprudential Encyclopedia" by Abu Ghanim Bashir bin Ghanim al-Khorasani in twelve parts. She was an eyewitness to the famous Battle of Manu in the year 283 AH, in which about 480 of the best Ibadi scholars were martyred, and she was taken captive along with others. They were among the best women of the Rustum tribe in their time. Although they did not have extensive knowledge of writing and reading, they were able to enlighten their societies with the knowledge that God had bestowed upon them. They were described as knowledgeable, learned, pious, and wise women, and women in their gatherings remember them as role models and emulate them for those qualities.

Keywords : The Rustumid state, Ibadi women, the Maghreb, thought and culture

Introduction

Throughout both ancient and modern times, women have stood beside men, supporting them as wives within the household, yet this did not prevent them from competing with and participating alongside men in many activities outside the home. All of this was pursued in search of lawful sustenance and for the upbringing of the family. Beyond that, women also entered the field of knowledge through its widest gates: they sat with scholars, authored works, and delivered speeches from pulpits, leaving behind a clear and lasting mark. They did so with modesty, dignity, and propriety, in accordance with the teachings of Islamic law.

The Rustamid woman was among those who contributed to the intellectual life of the Rustamid state throughout its 136 years of existence. Many distinguished women emerged across the various regions where Ibādism spread in the Maghreb, from Nafusa in the east to Ouargla in the south, passing through Djerba, the Jerid region, Wadi Souf, Arigh, and Mzab. The discussion of all those women who left notable contributions in the fields of rational and transmitted sciences would be extensive. They became particularly renowned in jurisprudence, legal theory, Qur'anic exegesis, Hadith, and everything related to religion and the Ibadi school of thought. Their opinions, sayings, and intellectual traces were often transmitted orally rather than in written form, circulating among women in both private and public gatherings. Some of these accounts were later documented in Ibadi biographical works, which preserved records of their virtues, merits, and scholarly as well as intellectual achievements.

The central research problem revolves around the following question: In what ways did Rustamid Ibadi women contribute to Islamic intellectual heritage in general, and to Ibadi heritage in particular? Through this study, we seek to highlight the achievements of Rustamid women in the field of knowledge by focusing on two exemplary Ibadi female scholars who lived during the Rustamid era. Both were acknowledged near and far for their scholarly brilliance, their influence on Rustamid society locally and regionally, and for the oral traditions and narrated accounts attributed to them, which were transmitted through various biographical and historical works.

Historians addressed the subject of Rustamid women within the broader context of their writings, though they rarely devoted independent chapters or sections specifically to them. Among the most notable studies is an article by the researcher Bouba Majani entitled *The Role of Women in the Scholarly Movement in Jabal Nafusa*. In it, she introduced an important source upon which she relied: *Sīrat Ahl Nafusa* by al-Baghtūrī, whose author paid significant attention to learned and pious women of the mountain region, whom he referred to as “the elderly women.” He included biographies of figures such as Umm Yaḥyā the jurist, Zūrgh al-Arjāniyya the mufti, Umm al-Khaṭṭāb the teacher, and others who rivaled male scholars. Their number reached approximately three hundred female jurists. However, the study did not provide many detailed accounts about them and remained largely general in nature.

Likewise, the researcher Fatima Mathari concluded in her article entitled *The Ibadi Woman and Her Contribution to the Cultural Movement in the Maghreb during the Medieval Period* that many Ibadi women distinguished themselves in the cultural sphere through their attendance at scholarly and juridical gatherings, their study of religion, and their teaching of women in their homes, in addition to their role in preserving the Ibadi doctrine up to the present day.

Among the most important studies dealing with the subject of the learned Rustamid woman are the Ibadi biographical works composed by Ibadi scholars, beginning with Luwāb ibn Salām (d. after 273 AH) and continuing up to Abū al-ʿAbbās Aḥmad al-Shammākhī (d. 928 AH). These biographical compilations gathered the lives and virtues of Ibadi scholars throughout the ages, and women also occupied an important place within them. However, these works generally lack detailed information concerning the essential aspects of the women's lives, focusing instead mainly on their reputation in jurisprudence, legal opinions, and teaching.

This study adopts a descriptive and analytical approach in order to examine the biographies of the two exemplary women through a close reading of the biographical source texts related to them, while also

clarifying their role in enriching scientific and cultural life in Tāhert, Jabal Nafusa, and the wider regions where Ibādism spread.

1.The Flourishing of the Scientific and Intellectual Movement in the Rustamid State (160–296 AH)

Asceticism and detachment from worldly pleasures were the dominant characteristics of the Rustamid Imams and the majority of the Ibadī Rustamid society. Renouncing earthly desires and temptations was regarded as a noble goal pursued by both the elite and common people, scholars and ordinary individuals alike, representing all social classes. For this reason, the educated class composed of scholars, sheikhs, imams, and students of knowledge devoted great attention to various transmitted, rational, and especially religious sciences. They spent enormous sums of money and exerted tremendous efforts to stimulate intellectual and scientific activity throughout the state by building mosques, educational institutions, and libraries, as well as importing books from the East, Sudan, and al-Andalus.

Among the most famous examples mentioned by historical sources is the al-Maʿsūmah Library in the capital, Tahert, which contained more than three thousand volumes, making it comparable to the renowned centers of Kairouan and Fez and their counterparts¹. The interest of the Rustamids both rulers and subjects in knowledge was not surprising, as it characterized them throughout their prosperous eras in the regions of the central and lower Maghreb where their territories extended. In particular, the reign of the third Imam, Aflah ibn ʿAbd al-Wahhab (d. 258 AH), is considered one of the brightest periods of Rustamid cultural and intellectual flourishing. Before him were held three circles of study in jurisprudence, theology, and language. He also authored responses and legal opinions concerning jurisprudential matters, and he attained remarkable expertise in arithmetic and astronomy. Furthermore, he was a man of letters and a poet, and his son Muhammad inherited his². knowledge of astronomy.

On the other hand, scholarly journeys undertaken by students, pilgrims, and even merchants played a major role in promoting learning. Political fragmentation and doctrinal differences between the Rustamid State and the Abbasid Caliphate did not hinder these exchanges. Rather, there existed strong communication and intellectual bridges between Tahert, Kairouan, and the Islamic East despite the tense political relations between the two sides. Cultural and scientific exchanges flourished through travel to and from Egypt, Baghdad, Damascus, and other centers. Ibadī biographical and historical works contain numerous accounts of Rustamid scholars and students who acquired knowledge in Tahert, Nafusa, Kairouan, and elsewhere. Likewise, students from Kairouan, Kufa, and Basra studied under the scholars of Tahert and Nafusa, demonstrating the vitality of learning among the Islamic cities beyond political influence and rivalry.

Knowledge was not confined to men alone. During the Rustamid era, many women, young girls, and wives emerged who took upon themselves the responsibility of enlightening the female Rustamid society and rescuing it from ignorance and illiteracy through education. Although women's participation remained somewhat limited compared to men, many of them succeeded in leaving a lasting mark in historical, biographical, and Ibadī literary sources throughout the centuries. This indicates the spread of learning and teaching among women across various Ibadī regions in the Islamic Maghreb, a tradition that continues to the present day.

¹ Rashid Bourouiba and al., *Algeria in History: The Islamic Era from the Conquest to the Beginning of the Ottoman Period*, Algeria: National, 1984, p. 111.

² Belhaj Maʿrouf, "Intellectual Production during the Rustamid State," *Al-Fada' al-Magharibi Journal*, no. 2, 2004, p. 242.

2. The Rustamid Woman in the Capital, Tahert

The woman was the true vessel of Ibādism and the first building block indeed the essential pillar of society. She faithfully carried and preserved the doctrine and played a major role in safeguarding the Rustamid family and its prominent men. Historical records recount a long list of women who were mothers, daughters, and wives of the sheikhs and rulers of the Rustamid state, as well as female servants and slave women who supported men. In addition, there were women who pursued knowledge and competed with men in libraries, mosques, and homes. Their occupations and social lives never prevented them from serving knowledge and its seekers, whether women or men.

The Rustamid capital, Tahert, witnessed a vibrant intellectual movement that flourished during the reign of its imams, especially in its early period under its founder, ‘Abd al-Raḥmān ibn Rustam, then his son Imam ‘Abd al-Wahhāb, followed by his son Aflah. Students of knowledge came to it from every direction. Historians described it as the “Iraq of the Maghreb.” Its mosques brought together Muslims of various ethnicities and sects, from both the Maghreb and the East, who studied under distinguished scholars in numerous fields. Its fame spread far and wide, and it left behind rich libraries whose influence reached the East, al-Andalus, and the lands of Sudan.

The Rustamid woman was not excluded from the world of learning previously dominated by men. Rather, she succeeded in competing with leading students and scholars in both rational and transmitted sciences. Evidence of this appears in biographical sources that mention women whose names shone in the intellectual circles of Tahert and throughout the Rustamid territories. These women enjoyed considerable freedom, broad influence, and deep devotion to religious practices. They also raised generations upon these principles and nurtured righteous successors. Knowledge even reached servants and slave women, becoming a means for freeing them from the chains of slavery, as many examples in biographical literature demonstrate. Abū Zakariyyā’ and al-Darjīnī said regarding members of such families: “God forbid that we should have a female slave who does not know the place where the moon spends the night.” If this was the case for slave women, what then of free women? Rustamid women also displayed remarkable intelligence and sound judgment. An example of this is when Sheikh Abū ‘Ubayda ‘Abd al-Ḥamīd al-Janāwanī consulted an elderly woman from Jabal Nafusa, renowned for her knowledge and piety, regarding his acceptance of the leadership of the mountain region entrusted to him by Imam ‘Abd al-Wahhāb. She advised him to accept and presented convincing arguments in support of her opinion.

Thus, women attained a distinguished status in knowledge, especially in jurisprudence. They attended scholarly and literary gatherings and opened their homes to scholars who held intellectual sessions there. Women also had gatherings specifically dedicated to them. Among them were female teachers who devoted themselves to spreading knowledge and strengthening the principles of Ibādī jurisprudence. One example is al-Ghāyah, the wife of the jurist Abū al-Qāsim Yazīd ibn Makhlad, the jurist of al-Ḥammah. Likewise, “Umm Yaḥyā” welcomed women into her home to teach them the matters of their religion. The home of “Umm al-Rabī’ al-Warīriyah” served as a refuge for virtuous people, and her wealth was dedicated to supporting students of knowledge. Meanwhile, the house of “Bahlūlah” became a destination for scholars. This reflects the high level of concern for learning in the state, to the extent that homes were used alongside mosques and Qur’anic schools to spread religious culture and knowledge. These women also earned an honorable reputation among jurists, and some of them reached the same level as men in mastery of jurisprudence and other Islamic sciences. History records a long list of women who left their mark in various scientific, cultural, social, and economic fields. Although accounts of their lives and achievements often appear only as brief references scattered within books, these references nevertheless reveal their significant contributions in all these areas. They succeeded in influencing Rustamid society in general and women in particular. Their names are numerous and are preserved in many Ibādī biographical and historical sources. They grew up in environments shaped by the geographical, political, economic, and social conditions of regions such as Djerba, Jabal Nafusa, the Jarid, Arigh, Souf, Ouargla, and Mzab throughout the centuries. Among them, by way of example and not limitation, are: Umm al-Bakht al-Mazzātiyyah,

Tabrakānt al-Sadrāṭiyyah, Bahlūlah al-Nafūsiyyah, Za‘īmah al-Bārūniyyah, and Mamma Bābāz al-Mīzābiyyah.

2.1. The Sister of Imam Aflah ibn Abd al-Wahhab

Among the women whose names were frequently mentioned and circulated in historical sources was the sister of Aflah ibn Abd al-Wahhab ibn Abd al-Rahman ibn Rustam, the third imam of the Rustamid state, who ruled between 208–258 AH / 823–871 CE. This learned woman’s full name, date of birth, death, and details of her broader social relations were not recorded by the sources. Thus, Ibadī biographical works referred to her simply as “the sister of Imam Aflah.” She belonged to the ruling Rustamid family in Tahert and was raised in her parents’ household. The mention of her name in biographical literature is evidence of her prominence as a knowledgeable and scholarly jurist among the women of Tahert, in addition to the virtues and learning for which she became renowned.

2.2. The Science of Inheritance and Mathematics According to Aflah’s Sister

The sources do not discuss the stages of her education and intellectual formation, yet this can be inferred through the biographical and classificatory works that mention her. These indicate that she frequently attended scholarly gatherings and study circles, most likely in Tahert, the capital, which was rich in mosques, educational institutions, and libraries. Learning often began during adolescence, especially for girls. The sources mention that one day she sat beside her brother Aflah while they studied the sciences of inheritance and arithmetic together. Dawn did not break upon them until they had mastered all the issues they were studying.¹

Her study of such subjects could only have taken place during youth or later, due to the complexity and precision of these disciplines, which would have been difficult for younger individuals to comprehend. The division of estates and the calculation of inheritance shares among male and female heirs constituted a science in itself, closely connected to arithmetic, or what is now called mathematics. Mastery of this field was essential in accordance with transmitted juristic rulings and legal principles. Their joint study of these two sciences reflects both their awareness of their importance and the scarcity of people capable of dealing with them in their time.

Researcher Virginie Prévost mentions that: “Imam Abd al-Wahhab, who ruled between 171–208 AH / 787–823 CE, spent one night with his sister studying inheritance issues, and by dawn they had determined the inheritance shares of all the inhabitants of the East and the West!” Although the account contains some exaggeration, it nevertheless demonstrates their profound mastery of inheritance law, a science later transmitted to his son Aflah and to Aflah’s sister. Likewise, Imam Aflah ibn Abd al-Wahhab, who ruled between 208–258 AH / 823–871 CE, would entertain his sister at night with problems in arithmetic and probability. One member of the Rustamid family even said: “God forbid that we should have a servant in our household who does not know the phases of the moon.”²

This statement reflects her extensive knowledge in sciences that could only have been acquired through long periods of study under scholars and teachers. Therefore, her sitting with her brother to study inheritance and arithmetic may be understood in several ways: either she was teaching her brother Aflah, who may not yet have possessed broad expertise in these sciences; or the two were examining difficult legal cases and practical problems that puzzled people; or they were reviewing previous lessons or preparing material for the following day.

The sources also mention that Aflah once spent a night conversing with his sister, discussing scholarly topics and literary arts. Like the rest of her family, she had been nourished by knowledge from an early age and possessed deep-rooted learning. Their conversation eventually turned to astrology. After discussing it at length, Aflah proposed that each of them predict the first animal to be slaughtered in

¹ Al-Shammakhi, *Al-Siyar*, 1/163.

² Abu Zakariyya Yahya ibn Abi Bakr al-Warjalani, *Kitab al-Sirah wa Akhbar al-A‘immah*, ed. Abd al-Rahman Ayoub, Tunis: al-Dar al-Tunisiyyah lil-Nashr, 1981, pp. 102–135.

the market the next day. After calculating, he said: “The first animal slaughtered will be a yellow cow carrying a white-marked calf in its womb.” She then made her own calculations and replied: “Your calculation is correct concerning the cow, its color, and the calf, but mistaken regarding the white mark. The calf has no white blaze; rather, the whiteness you inferred from your calculations is at the tip of the calf’s tail, which is curled up so that it appears upon its forehead.” The next morning, he ordered that the first slaughtered animal be brought before him, and it appeared exactly as his sister had described, without discrepancy.¹

From this narrative, we perceive the sister’s superiority over her brother in astrology, though intuition may also have played a role. How else could they have known what animal would be slaughtered in the market the following day? Perhaps the matter was based on prior information known to the siblings, such as the arrival that day of a group of cattle intended for sale or slaughter. Thus, they may have built their predictions on such observations. On the other hand, the account also reveals the brother’s humility before his sister, his respect for her, and his acknowledgment of her accurate intelligence. It further suggests that this science was widespread among both the elite and the common people, and Aflah’s sister’s interest in it is evidence of that fact. Women undoubtedly sought her out because of her expertise.

2.3. Its Impact on Society:

The sister of Imam Aflah was known for her knowledge of arithmetic, astronomy, and astrology, and she became famous for her debates with her brother Aflah. Historical sources unanimously attest to² her mastery and expertise in these sciences. As researchers, we may ask why she was so devoted to learning and education on the one hand, and particularly to the rational sciences on the other, despite being a housewife and a married woman. Yet, this did not prevent her from pursuing knowledge. The answer to this question seems to lie in the Islamic principle that seeking knowledge is an individual obligation upon every Muslim man and woman alike. The verses of Surat Al-‘Alaq do not specify the gender of the learner, but rather address both males and females. Moreover, religious sciences were already widespread among the women of her time, whether free women or servants, and thus it was not necessarily essential to focus on what was already common among the public and scholars alike. In addition, these sciences were no longer restricted to men. Perhaps the scarcity of students interested in them and their reluctance to study them motivated her to delve into these fields and excel in them. Arithmetic, or mathematics, was closely related to the science of inheritance and Islamic shares (*farā’id*), while astronomy had a direct connection with the Islamic months and pillars of Islam such as fasting, pilgrimage, and other acts of worship. As for astrology, it consists of traditions and beliefs that associate the positions and movements of celestial bodies such as stars and planets with earthly or personal events, and it is used to draw astrological charts for personality analysis and future prediction. Astrology differs completely from astronomy, which raises the question: why was the sister of Abd al-Wahhab interested in it?

The likely answer is the spread of doctrinal and religious deviations among the vulnerable segments of Rustamid society, especially women. Therefore, she may have sought to study astrology in order to confront fortune-tellers, sorcerers, charlatans, and impostors, particularly within women’s circles. This also indicates the spread of superstitions and innovations in the society of Tahert, where various religions and beliefs coexisted alongside Islam in its different forms. Such coexistence reflects the Rustamid spirit of tolerance toward different peoples and ethnic groups. Although astrology was generally considered forbidden across Islamic schools of thought, her interest in these sciences alongside transmitted sciences such as Qur’anic exegesis, theology, and jurisprudence enabled her to

¹ Abu Zakariyya, *Al-Sirah*, p. 136; Sulayman ibn Abd Allah Pasha al-Baruni, *Al-Azhar al-Riyadiyyah fi A’immat wa Muluk al-Ibadiyyah (Part Two)*, ed. Ahmad Karum et al., Constantine: Dar al-Ba‘th, 2002, p. 255.

² Abu Zakariyya Yahya ibn Abi Bakr al-Warjalani, *Kitab al-Sirah wa Akhbar al-A’immah*, ed. Abd al-Rahman Ayyub, Tunis: al-Dar al-Tunisiyyah lil-Nashr, 1981, pp. 102–135.

disseminate various forms of knowledge among the women and daughters of Tahert, rescuing them from ignorance and illiteracy so that they might worship God with understanding. Through this, we may also infer the extent to which these sciences were widespread among women as well as men. There is little doubt that books and manuscripts on these sciences once existed in the libraries of Tahert, such as the Ma'ṣūmah Library, and were perhaps burned along with other works during the Fatimid Shiite campaigns against the Maghreb in 296 AH.

In conclusion, the texts that mention the sister of Imam Aflah do not discuss her social life or daily interactions with her family, neighbors, and other women in society. Rather, they consistently portray her within scholarly gatherings. Her specialization in inheritance law, arithmetic, and astrology reflects her persistent commitment to educating herself both religiously and intellectually and transmitting this knowledge to women in society. She took upon herself the responsibility of teaching women their religious duties and the various sciences mentioned above. In this regard, she represents a model of the learned and scholarly Rustamid woman of Tahert who recognized no limits in the pursuit and dissemination of knowledge.

3-The Rustamid Woman in Jabal Nafusa

Early and later scholars wrote extensively about the sheikhs and scholars of Jabal Nafusa during the medieval period. Numerous articles, theses, and academic conferences have also addressed this subject. Perhaps the most important historical source discussing the male and female scholars of Nafusa is the book of al-Baghturi, edited by the researcher Tawfiq Ayyad al-Shaqruni under the title *Siyar al-Baghturi*. It was later edited by the researcher Omar Luqman Bou'asbana under the title *Narratives of the Sheikhs: The Sheikhs of Jabal Nafusa, Famous as Siyar al-Baghturi*. Its author devoted particular attention to learned and righteous women of the mountain, whom he referred to as "the elderly women"¹ or "the righteous elderly women." Among them were Zurugh al-Arjaniyyah, Umm Yahya from Tisasalit (or Timsalit), referred to in contemporary sources as Tamulast, Asit from Wighu, Asil from Timsams, Sarghint from Waryuri, Umm Hasanun from Lalut, Sidnat from Tamlushayt, Tujint, Umm Aman from Tardayat, and Umm Ayyub from Masliyush.²

The researcher Virginie Prevost classified these women into groups according to the qualities for which they became known. The first group consisted of educated and cultured Ibadi women recognized for their expertise in jurisprudence, Qur'anic exegesis, and various sciences. The second group included inspired Ibadi women renowned for miracles, supernatural feats, and wonders. The third group comprised highly pious Ibadi women distinguished by asceticism, devotion, religiosity, and answered prayers.³ In each category, she mentioned women who became famous among the Ibadi communities of Jabal Nafusa during the medieval era.

Religiosity appears to have been the common characteristic shared by all three categories. In reality, these groups overlap considerably, as there was a close connection between women's piety, their religious education, and their inclination toward miracles or preaching. One term consistently associated with these women is "al-'ajuz" (the elderly woman), a word usually used for an older woman, but which in Ibadi sources seems to describe Berber women possessing these three qualities. Many of the women mentioned in Ibadi narratives are presented as elderly women, although they do not necessarily appear to have been advanced in age in order to possess such qualities, even though old age is often linked with wisdom in many societies.⁴ Widowhood, which is mentioned several times

¹ Collective Authors, *Dictionary of Ibadi Figures (Maghreb Section)*, Ghardaia: Arab Printing House, 1999, Vol. 2, p. 119.

² Bouba Majani: *The Role of Women in the Scientific Movement in Jabal Nafusa from the Third to the Sixth Century AH*, *Al-Hayat Journal*, no. 2, January 1999, p. 158.

³ Virginie Prevost, *ibid.*, pp. 339–344.

⁴ Virginie Prevost: *Berber women in the Ibadi sources of the medieval Maghreb*, in *Written Sources about Africa and Their Study*, edited by Mena Lafkioui and Vermondo Brugnatelli, Rome–Milan: Bulzoni-Ambrosiana, 2018, p. 338.

in the narratives, also does not seem to have been a condition for attaining this distinguished status. We may therefore imagine the “elderly woman” as the female counterpart of the “shaykh,” who enjoyed high esteem in Ibadi sources. These women were often married and had children and grandchildren, yet this did not prevent them from seeking and acquiring knowledge.

One of the most important reasons behind Nafusa women’s interest in learning was the decline in the number of sheikhs due to wars, or because many of them left for trade in the lands of Western Sudan. This created opportunities for women to pursue education, especially in jurisprudence. Evidence of this can be seen in the appointment of a woman, Umm Yahya, to oversee the religious affairs of the mountain when the men left to fight the Aghlabids in the famous Battle of Manu in 283 AH. Some scholars even state that one-third of the mountain’s knowledge was possessed by a woman known as Zurugh al-Arjaniyyah.¹

The geographical location of the mountain and its villages, spread across its slopes, greatly contributed to its tranquility and relative distance from the wars and unrest that affected the coastal and desert regions, such as Tripoli and its surroundings, the island of Djerba, and their shores. This made Jabal Nafusa a fortified stronghold difficult to conquer. Consequently, its society and women in particular enjoyed considerable freedom of movement between villages in pursuit of knowledge in homes, mosques, and under the guidance of local sheikhs over a long period. This environment enabled the emergence of learned women scholars distinguished in religion, legal opinions, and various other fields of knowledge, carrying the banner of learning and spreading it throughout their communities.

Al-Baghturi listed forty-four free and enslaved women who were engaged in various branches of knowledge and who excelled in disciplines traditionally reserved for men. Many of them were not clearly identified by personal names, but rather by reference to their sons, such as Umm Zayd and Umm Za‘rur. Others were identified by their own names and attributed to their husbands, such as Bahlulah, the wife of Aban, and Talluli, the wife of Abu Muhasir al-Afatmani. Some were identified by their tribe or village, such as Asiyah from the people of Wighu and Umm Yahya Taksalit from the people of Jalimah. However, the sources do not provide detailed biographies of their lives; instead, they merely offer brief references to the sciences and arts for which these women became known among people and among other women. This concise style is characteristic of Ibadi biographical literature.

3.1. Tuzzin, the Sister of Sheikh ‘Amrūs ibn Fath

Knowledge became widespread among the women of the Nafusa Mountains, and they attained a high degree of learning. Education spread not only among free women but also among female servants and slaves. The clearest evidence of this is what al-Wisyānī mentioned in his *Sīra*:

“Knowledge became so widespread and common in the mountain that even their servants and slave women, when they went out to fetch water, would not return before discussing issues from the Book of *Mātūs*, which contained three hundred questions, as well as the admonitions found in the Book of the Brethren.”²

This demonstrates the spread of learning and culture among the women of the mountain, whether free or enslaved, to the extent that they memorized legal questions and religious rulings by heart. This is not surprising when we know that most of this knowledge was transmitted orally. Only a few women were able to write, since they were Berbers and found it difficult to learn Arabic except for what related to acts of worship such as prayer and religious rulings.

¹ Elderly people represent the wisdom of society; they are familiar with its traditions and customs, possess experience acquired through long lives, and are generally more committed to religious teachings than impulsive youth.

² Abu al-Rabi‘ Sulayman ibn Abd al-Salam al-Wisyani: *Siyar al-Wisyani*, edited and studied by Omar Sulayman Bou‘asbana, Amman: Ministry of Heritage and Culture, 2009; al-Shammakhi: *Al-Siyar*, 2/378.

Sources mention that their number reached approximately three hundred elderly women or female jurists in the coastal region alone. This figure concerns the medieval period and is considered large¹ given the relatively small population of each village in the Nafusa Mountains. However, the sources do not clarify whether this number referred specifically to free women, slave women, or both together. Ibadī sources used the term “‘ajūz” (elderly woman) to refer to a learned and knowledgeable female jurist, in contrast to the term “shaykh” used for a male jurist.² Women were often addressed as “Nānā Ūlālā” within both female and male society. In a period closer to our own time, the term “Nānā,” which originally meant “grandmother,” appears to have replaced the term “‘ajūz.” We found this term only once in medieval Ibadī texts, where al-Baghaṭūrī used it in a dialogue between women.³

Today, the term is commonly used for a pious woman, at least in the Nafusa Mountains. In the Mزاب region, however, the term “Lallā” or “Lāllah” seems to be used instead of “Nānā” or “Nānah.” The simplicity and ease of pronunciation of these expressions convey humility and closeness to people’s hearts. Although terms such as “teacher,” “instructor,” or even “female jurist” and “scholar” could be used within women’s society, such titles might imply pride or vanity, which is contrary to Islamic ethics. Moreover, most of these elderly learned women possessed only limited skills in reading and writing. Whatever broad knowledge they had in various sciences was transmitted orally and memorized from earlier learned women or acquired from sheikhs in study circles held in mosques and homes.

3.2. Tuzzin bint Fath: The Jurist, Scribe, and Mufti

Among the distinguished elderly women of Nafusa, we have chosen Tuzzin, the sister of Sheikh Amrūs ibn Fath al-Masakini. She was a noble and virtuous woman, married to a righteous and honorable man. Abu Zakariyya described her in his historical accounts as a learned jurist whose knowledge illuminated the darkness of the mountain region for a long period, especially during times of wars and battles when men were absent.

Some of the available sources mention her name, while the inhabitants of Jabal Nafusa have preserved her memory and passed down her name through generations. She is known as Tuzzin bint Fath al-Masakini, a name derived from the village of Masakin in the mountain region, which today is known as the village of Qatras in al-Rahibat. The dates of her birth and death remain unknown, though it is likely that she lived between 250–300 AH (864–913 CE). A prayer place bearing her name still exists in the aforementioned village.

She became renowned for her knowledge, piety, and wisdom, attaining a high level of expertise in various branches of learning. She and her brother are credited with copying the famous Ibadī jurisprudential compendium by Abu Ghanim Bashir ibn Ghanim al-Khurasani, consisting of twelve volumes and known as Al-Mudawwana or Al-Ghanimiyya.⁴

Tuzzin herself witnessed the famous Battle of Manu in 283 AH, during which nearly 480 prominent Ibadī scholars were martyred. She issued religious rulings (fatwas) for women who had fallen captive to the Aghlabids, guiding them in ways that would preserve their honor and faith; she herself was among the captives. [She advised that each woman appoint someone on her behalf to marry her to⁵ any man who sought her with ill intentions, out of fear that they might otherwise suffer corruption in their honor and religion.⁶

¹ Al-Wisyānī, *Sīra*, 2/234.

² Malīkah Ḥumaydī, “Women’s Care for Religious Sciences in the Islamic West between the 2nd and 6th Centuries AH,” *Journal of the Ministry of Religious Affairs and Endowments*, no. 7, 2010, p. 75.

³ Būbah Majānī, *The Role of Women in the Scholarly Movement in Jabal Nafusa*, p. 162.

⁴ Al-Baghaṭūrī, *Sīra*, pp. 43, 145. Regarding the term “Nānā,” see also:

M. Beaussier, M. Ben Cheneb, and A. Lentin, *Dictionnaire pratique arabe-français*, Paris: Ibis Press, 2006, p. 957.

⁵ Nabila Abdel Shakour, *Women in Ibadī Historiography*, *Al-Turath Journal*, Issue 12, 2014, p. 99.

⁶ Abu Zakariyya, *Al-Sirah*, p. 157.

This account is particularly significant because it demonstrates the participation of women alongside fighters during that period. Women served as strong supporters and helpers to the combatants. Moreover, it was not only ordinary women of the mountain who took part in wars, but even female jurists, who chose to stand beside their husbands in times of prosperity and hardship alike, assisting them by providing water and food, treating wounds, and carrying weapons until victory was achieved or martyrdom was attained in the path of God.

3.3 Its Influence on the Nafusa Society:

Tuzzin bint Amrūs played an important cultural role in the Nafusa Mountains. She accompanied her brother in his studies, listening to him and learning from him. Her brother, Shaykh Fath ibn Amrūs, served as the judge of Jabal Nafusa during the final years of the Rustamid state. She was considered his primary assistant in copying the compilation of Abu Ghanim Bishr ibn Ghanim al-KhurasaniIbadi¹ sources mention that she used to dictate the text to him, and whenever he sat down to copy the manuscript in one place, she would remain beside him until the sun reached him. Then he would move into the shade while the original manuscript remained in his sister's hands, his eyes fixed on the book without distraction, out of devotion to preserving knowledge. In this way, they succeeded in copying the entire work. Had it not been for the dedication of Amrūs and his sister in reproducing the compilation, the followers of the Ibadi school in the Maghreb would not have retained a reliable reference work after Tahert was destroyed and its books were burned.²

From this account, we can observe the extent of her commitment to seeking knowledge alongside her brother Amrūs, who was also her teacher and the chief judge of the mountain region in his time. Despite his official responsibilities, he remained supportive of his sister, who possessed a deep passion for learning. We also notice Tuzzin bint Amrūs's mastery of the Arabic language and its branches, as she dictated the lines of the compilation word by word a task beyond the capability of most women of that era. Shaykh Amrūs likely encouraged her education in preparation for such a day, so that she could assist him and he could rely upon her. Despite the enormous size of the compilation, consisting of large volumes, neither of them was discouraged from copying it. Through their determination to preserve the manuscript from being lost, they rendered a great service to the (Islamic nation).

Nafusa and the mountain region were therefore in urgent need of learned women who could explain matters of religion and Islamic law to women, especially considering that Nafusa was a Berber tribe and that the Arabic language was difficult to access and generally restricted to elite men. Consequently, it became necessary for a group of women to become knowledgeable in their religion through Arabic in order to transmit that knowledge to the wider female Nafusa community.³

This was the established tradition of Ibadi women since the medieval period. Throughout different historical eras and across all the regions where Ibadism spread in the Maghreb, Ibadi women were both educated and educators of other women, despite the hardships and crises that affected their communities. They fulfilled their role as teachers who contributed to the formation of a virtuous society rooted in Islam and the Arabic language, a legacy that continues to this day.

A study conducted by Amélie-Marie Goichon in the Mzab region at the beginning of the twentieth century concluded that Ibadi women had long enjoyed a level of education and authority uncommon in the Islamic world. Women's education remained the norm in respected Mzabi families. After childhood, women received continuous doctrinal and moral instruction throughout their lives under the supervision of a female religious organization.⁴

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² Ibrahim Bahaz, *The Rustamid State (160–296 AH / 777–909 CE): A Study of Economic Conditions and Intellectual Life*, Constantine: Ministry of Religious Affairs and Endowments, 2015, p. 323.

³ Al-Darjini, *Tabaqat*, 2/138; Al-Wisyani, *Siyar*, 1/234.

⁴ Amélie-Marie Goichon, *La vie féminine au Mzab: Étude de sociologie islamique*, Paris: Paul Gauthner, 1927, p. 15.

Conclusion:

The Rustamid Ibadī woman whether in Tahert, Nafusa Mountains, or other Ibadī centers such as Djerba, Jerid, Oued Righ, Souf, Ouargla, and Mزاب played a prominent role in the scientific and cultural movement. Many learned and reform-minded women emerged there, such as the sister of Imam Aflah and Tuzzin, the sister of, both of whom were among the distinguished female scholars of the Rustamid state, an era that witnessed the rise of numerous learned women, both free and enslaved alike.

The sister of Imam Aflah represented the model of the educated Rustamid woman of Tahert, highly skilled in the sciences of inheritance law, mathematics, and astrology. What helped her pursue knowledge and learning was the scholarly environment of the Rustamid household, which embraced many sciences, including jurisprudence, language, Qur'anic exegesis, Hadith, mathematics, medicine, astronomy, and astrology. She thus descended from the Rustamid lineage generation after generation, as the imams and rulers of the state were highly distinguished in knowledge and jurisprudence. Their daughters and wives followed the same path. Rustamid women did not limit themselves to teaching girls only the matters of religion; rather, they mastered various sciences, although most of them specialized in transmitted religious sciences, especially the study of the Ibadī doctrine. However, despite their fame and distinction in scholarship, their achievements remained confined to biographical and historical works, which rarely mentioned any writings or books they may have authored. It is also possible that such works were destroyed along with the contents of the Ma'suma Library of Tahert when the state fell to the Shiite Fatimids.

As for the mountainous region located in the far east of the state, it too produced outstanding women who carried the torch of knowledge. Among them was Tuzzin, the sister of Amrous, the jurist and compiler, who represented the model of the rural mountain woman scholar and struggler. She spared no effort in studying alongside her brother, Judge Amrous, and assisting him in compiling the Ibadī Ghanami jurisprudential compilation. Her mastery of the Arabic language and legal rulings was clear evidence of why her brother entrusted her with copying the compilation an immense responsibility undertaken jointly by the judge brother and the mufti sister.

Rustamid women exerted every possible effort to strengthen and spread the Ibadī doctrine. They worked to disseminate it through all available means, teaching in their homes and enduring hardships while studying with the leading scholars and sheikhs of the doctrine in their homes in order to deepen their understanding of both religious and worldly matters. They were also generous in sharing their knowledge with other women and never concealed what they had learned. Instead, they devoted themselves and their time to serving their society in both worldly and spiritual affairs.

In addition, the Berber language, which was widespread across the Maghreb and especially among women, gave learned women an important role as intermediaries who translated religious sciences and fatwas into Arabic and simplified them for other women. Nor should we overlook the role of the institution of the, locally known as "Tamsiridin" (the washers), who formed the social framework that nurtured those learned female jurists. This institution dates back to the establishment of the Azzaba circle by in 409 AH.

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